

Response of rice to potassium

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We studied the response of irrigated rice to K applied at different crop stages for two consecutive cropping seasons (1987-88). Treatments (see table) were in a randomized complete block design with

four replications.

Soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with 135 kg available K, 0.23% organic C, and 13.0 kg Olsen's P/ha. All plots received 120 kg N and 13 kg P/ha. All P and 1/3 N were applied just before transplanting; the remaining N was applied at 21 and 42 d after transplanting. Sources of N, P, K were urea, single superphosphate, muriate of potash, respectively.

Yield responded significantly to split application of 50 kg K/ha (1/2 at transplanting + 1/2 at active tillering) (see table). Split application of K at transplanting and panicle initiation and at active tillering and panicle initiation also significantly increased yield in 1988. Applying 100 kg K at transplanting was as efficient as split application. K helped increase panicle-bearing tillers and grain weight. □

Effect of K application on grain yield and some yield components. Punjab, India, 1987-88.

K (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Effective shoots (no./hill)		Grains (no./panicle)		1000-grain wt (g)	
	1987	1988	1987	1988	1987	1988	1987	1988
0 (control)	6.8	6.2	11.0	9.8	170	155	24.5	23.8
50 (all at transplanting)	7.1	6.6	11.5	10.6	174	160	25.1	24.5
50 (½ at transplanting + ½ at active tillering)	7.3	6.9	12.3	11.5	169	159	25.4	24.9
50 (½ at transplanting + ½ at panicle initiation)	7.2	6.9	11.7	11.6	176	158	25.3	25.1
50 (½ at active tillering + ½ at panicle initiation)	7.2	6.8	11.5	11.4	178	156	25.4	25.3
100 (all at transplanting)	7.4	7.1	12.5	11.6	177	154	25.7	25.3
100 (½ at transplanting + ½ at active tillering)	7.3	7.0	12.4	11.5	176	159	25.6	25.2
100 (½ at transplanting + ½ at panicle initiation)	7.5	7.0	12.6	11.8	171	158	25.4	25.4
100 (½ at active tillering + ½ at panicle initiation)	7.3	7.1	12.3	11.7	174	160	25.7	25.3
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.6	1.2	1.6	ns	ns	0.82	1.01

Effect of urea supergranule depth of placement in irrigated transplanted rice

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We conducted field trials at the BHU Research Farm during 1984 and 1985 rainy seasons. Urea supergranule (USG) and neem cake USG were placed at three depths (5, 10, and 15 cm) at three N levels (60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha). Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.4, 205.2 kg available N/ha, 13.8 kg available P/ha, and 171.7 kg available K/ha. The crop was irrigated as needed to maintain soil moisture between saturation and field capacity. All the N through USG was applied 1 wk after transplanting of rice variety Jaya, when soil moisture content was between field capacity and soil saturation. USG was applied at specified depths in the center of hills, with the help of a peg.

Effect of USG amount and depth of placement on transplanted irrigated rice.^a Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Protein content (kg/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		
			Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Total
<i>Placement depth (cm)</i>							
5	3.9	4.9	360	120	60	20	80
10	4.3	5.9	430	170	70	30	100
15	4.0	5.6	370	130	60	30	90
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.1	na	na	ns	ns	na
<i>N source</i>							
USG	3.9	5.6	380	140	60	20	80
Neem cake/USG	4.2	6.0	420	170	70	30	100
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	na	na	ns	ns	na
<i>N applied (kg/ha)</i>							
60	3.4	5.6	310	140	50	20	70
120	4.2	6.0	430	170	60	40	100
180	4.7	6.6	520	230	80	40	120
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.6	na	na	ns	ns	na

^aAv of 2 yr, 1984-85. ns = not significant, na = not analyzed.

Grain and straw yields were significantly higher with deep point placement of USG; placement 10 cm deep resulted in the highest yields, followed by that at 15 cm and 5 cm (see table). Protein harvest and N uptake were also highest under 10-cm-deep

placement.

USG treated with neem cake proved somewhat better than USG. Application of 180 kg N/ha gave significantly higher grain and straw yields as well as protein yield and N uptake. None of the interaction effects were significant. □